

Instruct-ERIC Pilot Node

A thematic node that provides access to structural biology services and techniques, with the interoperability services provided in EOSC Beyond to reach more researchers across Europe

FACTSHEET FOR: Researchers; Instruct Facilities; Instruct member countries/institutions; Education/training organisation/learners

Pilot Node Profile

To support our researchers and facilities, the node has been extended with storage brokering service via our management platform ARIA provisioned by Instruct FandanGo (a facility side workflow and data management toolchain) using storage services supplied by EGI via the EOSC Polish node.

The node is able to store raw experimental data within OneData which is linked to the researcher record held in ARIA. These data will then be published via EOSC Sandbox after an embargo period to reach a wider researcher base, and to make the data FAIR.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI**
Federated login to access services {in development}
- **Helpdesk**
Node support on services on Discovery Hub {beta}

Pilot Exchange Services

- **ARIA**
(cloud, storage, access instruments, workflow management)
- **FANDANGO**
(data management, storage)

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.

It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

User story at-a-glance

A researcher visits a smaller Instruct facility to perform some structural biology research.

Raw data is produced after the experiment and these data to be stored somewhere public which can then be accessed as future reference to other researchers.

Before: Oversight of raw data is lost after the experiment as insufficient storage available at smaller facilities. Data is handed to the user, with no ability for us to link it to the original research or to ensure FAIR data compliance.

After: Raw data can be accessed both in ARIA via a link from OneData, these data are to be made FAIR to a wider scientific community automatically after the embargo period has been reached.

Instruct-ERIC Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandbox and other Pilot Nodes

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- Discovery Hub
- AAI (in progress)
- Service catalogue (in progress)

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- Provides CESSDA instruments for booking system
- EGI Data Hub and Storage
- Helpdesk

Value of the Node piloting activities

Provision of storage for raw data:

Provision of storage made available across EOSC, enabling secure and scalable data preservation.

Combine resources:

Sharing knowledge, ideas and resources between nodes strengthening collaboration.

Discover more and faster:

Use enhanced search capabilities to find relevant data across EOSC

Strengthen Open Science:

Demonstrated practical pathways to make research data discoverability, interoperability, and reuse across the scientific community.

Strengthen the network:

Collaboration between various nodes has established shared standards, developed skills, and validated trusted workflows to ensure a sustainable federated network.

Next steps

Data Storage:

Ability to request storage from ARIA, capacity management for the allocated storage, and adding brokering functions within ARIA.

Discovery Hub:

Make raw data storage available in Research Product Catalogue.

Service Catalogue:

Onboard Exchange services.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

Instruct-ERIC Pilot Node:

<https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/instruct-eric>

Instruct-ERIC:

<https://instruct-eric.org/>